

READINESS, ATTITUDE, PERCEPTION, AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS ONLINE LEARNING AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Readiness, Attitude, Perception, and Satisfaction towards Online Learning among Medical Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the influence of readiness, attitude, and perception on online learning satisfaction among medical students. The strengths and weaknesses of current online learning practices were identified by examining these dimensions, and insights that can help enhance the design and delivery of online medical education were provided. Descriptive correlational and causal research designs were employed. Raosoft calculation was used to determine the sample size of 149 from a population of 173. Questionnaires were the basis for measuring the variable elements. A five-point Likert type of questionnaire was used for the data collection. Data was collected from students at the College of Medicine at Liceo de Cagayan University. The mean and standard deviation were used to describe the study's parameters. Pearson product-moment correlation and multiple linear regression were used to identify the best predictor of satisfaction with online learning. The students are prepared (Mean = 3.84, SD = 0.970) to engage in online educational environments. The study participants have moderately positive attitudes (Mean = 3.31, SD = 1.049) towards online learning and a moderately perceived understanding (Mean = 3.27, SD = 1.047) and interpretation of the online educational environment. Students have moderate satisfaction (Mean = 3.46, SD = 0.934) with online learning. Readiness ($r = 0.713$, $p < .001$), attitude ($r = 0.840$, $p < .001$), and perception ($r = 0.865$, $p < .001$) significantly correlate with satisfaction with online learning. The best predictor of online learning is medical students' perception ($\beta = 0.495$, $p < .001$) of online learning.

Keywords: *medical students, online environment, perception, attitude, readiness, understanding*

Introduction

The rapid advancement of digital technology has significantly transformed the education landscape, making online learning a viable alternative to traditional face-to-face instruction. This transformation is particularly relevant in medical education, where the integration of online learning platforms has become increasingly prevalent. The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated this shift, compelling educational institutions worldwide to adapt quickly to remote teaching methods. Despite the growing adoption of online learning, its effectiveness and acceptance among medical students remain subjects of ongoing investigation.

The readiness of students to engage with online learning, their attitudes towards this mode of education, their perceptions of its efficacy, and their overall satisfaction are crucial factors that influence the success of online education programs (Luu, 2022). Understanding these factors is especially important in medical education, where the quality of training directly impacts future healthcare professionals' competencies and the quality of patient care.

In early 2022, The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) resumed face-to-face classes in every institution. The continuation of online learning has produced a hybrid education model encompassing both advantages and disadvantages (Anzaldo, 2021). While incorporating online learning provides more flexibility and accessibility, thus enabling students to learn at their own pace from anywhere, it also complicates the situation by raising questions about maintaining uniform engagement and quality in different learning spaces (Culduz, 2024). The hybrid format can exploit the strengths of both pedagogical approaches, such as direct interaction among the students during classes and easy access to resources common with distance learning. However, balancing these two modalities will require proper planning and assistance so that neither is compromised. Shifting between online and face-to-face interactions is a challenge for learners and instructors who must deal with inconsistencies in the educational experience affected by various factors.

According to Damayon (2022), some significant problems in students' satisfaction with online learning are psychological issues, lack of social integration, and platform problems. These may hinder online learning satisfaction and cause distress for students and teachers. In the Philippines, Innoeduca (2023) highlighted that there is negative impact of on online learning satisfaction among the students, suggesting a need for reevaluation of teaching strategies to enhance virtual learning experiences.

In the studies involving satisfaction with online learning, researchers are contented with the motivation, and the lack of resources contributes to dissatisfaction with online learning. Recent research might examine learners' perceptions of fairness regarding access to resources, grading practices, and interaction opportunities in online courses (Rasooli et al., 2019) However, there are limited studies concerning attitude, readiness, and perception variables that might predict satisfaction in learning, particularly in the transition from a distance learning modality to an in-person class in the Philippines and other countries.

This study investigates medical students' readiness, attitude, perception, and satisfaction with online learning. By examining these dimensions, we seek to identify the strengths and weaknesses of current online learning practices and provide insights that can help enhance the design and delivery of online medical education. The findings of this research will contribute to the broader discourse on the effectiveness of online learning in professional education and offer practical recommendations for educators and policymakers to

improve the online learning experience for medical students.

Methodology

Research Design

The nature of this study requires the use of a descriptive correlational and causal research design. The purpose of descriptive research is to characterize the phenomenon and its characteristics. This study is more interested in what happened than how or why it happened (Nasajji, 2015). Although data from these studies can be collected qualitatively, they are often studied statistically, using statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and means to find relationships. About this study, problems 1-4 require a descriptive research design.

The design of a predictive correlation study is useful not only for examining relationships between the same variables in two populations or the same variables in two groups of people (Curtis et al., 2016) but also provides scope in which the behavior model of the criterion can be explained (Jenkins, 2015) and the variance of one or more variables can be predicted based on the variance of another variable.

Since this study embraces the methodologies of the predictive-correlational design, quantitative data were first obtained from the medical student respondents through survey questionnaires.

Meanwhile, causal research design investigates cause relationships. To determine causality, variation in the variable presumed to influence the difference in another variable must be detected, and then the variations from the other variable must be calculated.

Respondents

This study included 149 medical students at Liceo de Cagayan University. To determine the sample size, it employed probability sampling using a stratified random technique.

Using probability sampling, the investigator is assured that every component of a known population is included. Using probability samples, rigorous analysis can be used to assess the likelihood and potential for bias and error. Random selection is the process of selecting the elements of a sample so that each person in the population has an equal probability of being chosen. The sample's characteristics are presumed to reflect those of the entire population from which it was selected. Hence, defining the sample frame is the first step in choosing a sample (Adwok, 2015).

The stratified random sampling approach is one method. This sampling technique creates smaller groupings (called strata) based on similar traits within the population. Next, from each, a random sample is collected and combined (in direct proportion to the stratum's size relative to the population (Qualtrics, 2021).

Table 1 shows the distribution of the participants of the study. It shows that of the total population of 173, using the Raosoft calculation, 149 constituted the sample size.

Table 1. *Respondents Distribution*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
1st	85	70
2nd	42	38
3rd	46	41
Total	173	149

Instrument

The study aimed to assess the satisfaction of medical students with online learning using four questionnaires. The first was the Readiness Questionnaire, which assessed readiness and effort in online learning. The second was the Attitude questionnaire, which evaluated students' conduct in online setup. The third was the researcher's perception of online learning, measuring students' positive perception-related countenance. The fourth was a researcher-made satisfaction tool on online learning. The quantitative data was collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Validity and reliability tests were used to determine the relationship between satisfaction with online learning and readiness, attitude, and perception among medical students. Multiple regression analysis was used to identify predictors of satisfaction on online learning.

Table 2. *Test of Internal Consistency Report*

<i>Scales</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
Readiness	0.880	10
Attitude	0.919	9
Perception	0.952	10
Satisfaction	0.949	10

Data for the study was collected from self-administered surveys. Four sets of questionnaires were used to measure satisfaction, readiness, attitude, and perception. The questionnaires were validated by three experts and tested for reliability, accuracy, and significance. The questionnaires were piloted with 30 medical students not included in the sample to ensure their reliability. The

university's data processor checked the research questionnaires for reliability. The internal consistency test was conducted to ensure the study's instruments were reliable.

Procedure

The investigator implemented a series of structured procedures to collect data for the study. Initially, instrument preparation and survey forms were created, with a unique identification number assigned to each questionnaire. Following this, approval was sought from the Dean of the College of Nursing, with formal letters delivered requesting authorization to distribute surveys to medical students and outlining the study's timeline. The next step involved personally meeting or connecting with participants online, during which informed consent forms were provided alongside the surveys. This step emphasized building trust through clear communication about the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and confidentiality. Ethical considerations were rigorously observed throughout the data gathering phase, reinforcing the importance of these principles for ensuring the credibility of the research. The investigator adhered to established protocols and criteria, including participant inclusion, informed consent, and privacy, thereby prioritizing ethical integrity in the research process.

The research focused on participant selection following the principle of justice to ensure a fair distribution of relevant measures. Strict inclusion and exclusion criteria were established: participants must be medical students from the College of Medicine at Liceo de Cagayan University, must consent to partake in the study, and will be chosen randomly in accordance with the study's nature and objectives. The immediate benefit to participants lies in the opportunity to express their satisfaction with online learning and evaluate various affective factors such as readiness, attitude, and perception. Additionally, the investigation aims to gather valid and reliable data on participants' productivity and performance levels, which could inform policy-making and contribute positively to the work culture. Ultimately, the research aims to foster a platform for participants to share their views on their current work conditions, benefiting both the educational institution and the broader learner community.

The study did not involve any monetary compensation or reimbursement for participants' expenses. A declaration addressing transparency and conflicts of interest was discussed prior to administering the research instruments, ensuring the integrity of the findings. The investigator confirmed that there were no competing interests related to financial or non-financial considerations. Participation was voluntary, allowing individuals to withdraw at any time, with respect for their choices. The sample consisted of 173 medical students from Liceo de Cagayan University, selected through stratified random sampling. The survey consisted of four sections addressing readiness, attitudes toward online learning, perceptions, and satisfaction. Participants could choose not to disclose their names, opting for a pseudonym instead. Each question required a single response, and participants were encouraged to provide honest answers. Completed surveys were collected for relevance to the study, and participants were informed of the investigator's contact details for any queries.

The survey administration allowed participants ample time to respond, with encouragement to seek clarifications from the researcher, who was available via email if they opted to complete the questionnaire at home. Participation was voluntary, and individuals could withdraw at any time, with the survey expected to take only 10 to 15 minutes. The investigator ensured that the questionnaire was free from bias related to race, gender, sexual orientation, religion, politics, and culture, emphasizing the importance of the research for public primary education management. Upon completion, the responses were treated confidentially, coded, and securely stored, with no identifying information disclosed in reports. The investigator maintained strict privacy protocols, adhering to the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

The researcher expresses a strong interest in presenting the study's findings at academic conferences dedicated to educational trends. Attendance at such events is viewed as an excellent opportunity to engage with contemporary studies and ideas in the education sector. Additionally, should the research be published in a journal, the investigator is eager to pursue this avenue, recognizing that it would enhance visibility beyond their immediate professional network. The researcher emphasizes the importance of securing a place for this work in the enduring archives of educational research, which would further contribute to the field.

Data Analysis

The researcher employed various statistical tools to analyze and interpret data effectively. For Problems 1 to 4, descriptive statistics, specifically the mean and standard deviation, were utilized. The mean served as the primary measure of central tendency, while standard deviation provided insights into the variations among responses relative to the mean, revealing how medical students' responses clustered or dispersed. In addressing Problem 5, the Pearson product-moment correlation was applied to examine the relationships between variables, indicating the strength of their associations. Problem 6 was approached using multiple linear regression to identify predictors of satisfaction in online learning. This method enabled the investigator to analyze the influence of various independent variables on students' satisfaction, elucidating the nature of inter-variable relationships.

Results and Discussion

This section details all the data gathered after the survey was conducted. Statistical analysis and tabular presentations were made to efficiently identify the readiness, attitude, and perception of medical students regarding satisfaction with online learning at Liceo de Cagayan University—College of Medicine.

For additional information on the participants, the total population of LDCU-COM during the conduct of the study was 173. Using Raosoft, at least 149 respondents were considered the sample size that satisfied a 2% margin of error. Most of these 149 participants were 25-27 years old (55%), and most were 1st year medical students (47%). Also, the college was predominated by female students (71%). On the other hand, 31 years old and above holds the lowest age group (3%), and the lowest year-level respondents are in the 2nd year (26%).

The First statement of the problem investigated the level of readiness among medical students at Liceo de Cagayan University. The study found that online learning readiness is a vital factor in assessing students' preparedness for online education, with key elements such as awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement significantly influencing this readiness. A study focused on the readiness of Liceo de Cagayan University medical students reveals that the highest mean score for preparedness is associated with access to a computer or tablet (4.38), indicating a favorable disposition towards online medical education. Medical students in the Philippines feel prepared to engage with clinical lessons and personal development online. Conversely, the aspect with the lowest mean score was reliable access to high-speed internet (3.53), suggesting variability in students' responses regarding this critical resource, which underscores the importance of students' preparedness, engagement, and satisfaction in online learning environments, as well as the necessity of robust ICT infrastructure and support to address distractions and anxiety, ultimately enhancing learning outcomes.

The second statement of the problem measured the level of attitude among medical students in Liceo de Cagayan University. The study shows that attitude of Liceo de Cagayan University (LDCU) medical students towards online learning is influenced by various factors, including perceptions, personal issues, and the e-learning environment. A study reveals that students exhibit a positive attitude toward online learning, particularly in terms of time management, as evidenced by the phrase "Online learning allows me to balance my studies with other responsibilities," which received the highest mean score of 3.68. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that online learning contributes positively to students' educational continuity and time management. Conversely, the statement "Online learning is as effective as face-to-face learning" garnered the lowest average score of 2.77, indicating a preference among some students for traditional classroom settings. Overall, the results support the notion that while online learning offers flexibility, it is not universally regarded as equivalent to in-person learning by all medical students.

The third statement of the problem investigated the level of perception among medical students in Liceo de Cagayan University. The findings revealed that medical student's perception in online learning significantly impacts student engagement and behavior. Research indicates a strong correlation between students' perceptions and their academic procrastination, with positive views leading to diminished procrastination, medical students reported a high mean score of 3.762 regarding the helpfulness of provided resources, suggesting that faculty support is crucial to their learning experience. However, students rated the effectiveness of online learning compared to traditional methods much lower, with a mean score of 2.709, indicating a preference for face-to-face education. This assertion that perceptions of online learning as inferior can be mitigated by enhancing perceived task value and teacher influence.

The fourth statement of the problem investigated the level of level of satisfaction on online learning among medical students in Liceo de Cagayan University. It has been found out that Student satisfaction in online learning significantly influences their readiness, attitude, and perceptions. A recent study focusing on medical students at Liceo de Cagayan University found that the statement regarding comprehensive and useful online course materials received the highest satisfaction score of 3.709, indicating a positive response from students regarding these materials, which enhances academic satisfaction. This aligns with previous research confirming the positive impact of blended and distance learning on student satisfaction and learning outcomes. Conversely, the statement about the online learning environment's engagement level received a lower score of 3.199, suggesting moderate satisfaction among students. This indicates that, while the course materials are well-received, the overall online learning experience could be improved, a sentiment echoed by other studies highlighting factors affecting student satisfaction, such as peer communication and module support.

The fifth statement of the problem investigated the possibility of a correlation between satisfaction and readiness, attitude, and perception among medical students. The study found Studies have shown a strong positive correlation between readiness and satisfaction in online learning among medical students at Liceo de Cagayan University. Additionally, research has highlighted the positive association between online learning readiness and satisfaction, with students who prefer online learning reporting higher satisfaction levels. Positive attitudes towards online learning, particularly in receptive skills like listening and reading, are influenced by affective, behavioral, and cognitive factors. Attitude towards online learning has been found to be positively correlated with satisfaction, emphasizing the importance of a positive attitude for increased satisfaction. Perception also plays a significant role in satisfaction with online learning, with interactive learning and perceived usefulness impacting satisfaction levels. Medical students' perception of online learning has been strongly linked to their satisfaction levels, with studies showing that perception, attitude, and readiness all contribute to satisfaction in online education.

The last statement of the problem explored which of the variables best predicts satisfaction with online learning among medical students. It has been found out that perception, readiness, and attitude were significant predictors of satisfaction in online learning, with perception being the strongest predictor. The regression model showed that these variables could predict online learning satisfaction accurately. The equation used in the model was $Y' = 0.312 + 0.460 X_1 + 0.337 X_2 + 0.137 X_3$, where X_1 is Perception, X_2 is Attitude, and X_3 is Readiness. The R^2 value of 0.843 indicated that the model explained 84.3% of the variation in satisfaction, with key significance shown through the F value of 262.826. Multicollinearity was also tested, with results showing no issues in the regression

model. Perception played the most significant role in determining satisfaction among the students, emphasizing the importance of how students view online learning in influencing their satisfaction levels.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions are presented:

The study at LDCU-COM involved 149 participants, mostly 25-27 years old (55%) and first-year medical students (47%). Female students comprised 71% of the sample. Most students are prepared for online medical education, with a high mean score of 4.38. The study shows positive attitudes towards online learning, especially in terms of time management. However, some students still prefer face-to-face classes. The resources provided to students were perceived as helpful, with high satisfaction on comprehensive course materials. Satisfaction with online learning was moderate, with no significant correlations found based on age, sex, or year level. Readiness, attitude, and perception were strong predictors of satisfaction in online learning. Perception had the most impact, followed by attitude and readiness. The model could explain 84.3% of the variation in satisfaction. Multicollinearity tests for readiness, attitude, and perception showed no issues, ensuring the reliability of the results.

Overall, medical students are “prepared” for online learning. They also have a moderately positive attitude towards online education. Moreover, medical students “moderately perceive” online learning, and lastly, medical students are “moderately satisfied” with online learning.

There is a significant relationship between satisfaction with online learning, readiness, attitude, and perception among medical students. This implies that the more ready the medical students are, the more positive their attitude towards online learning, and the more they perceive positively, the more satisfaction they have with online learning.

The study's null hypothesis is rejected, claiming that no variable best predicts satisfaction in online learning. Perception, attitude, and readiness best predict satisfaction in online learning.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are put forward:

Commission of Higher Education (CHED) may offer to implement quality assurance mechanisms to maintain the standard of online courses. Course content, assessments, and feedback mechanisms may be reviewed to ensure relevance and effectiveness.

Medical Faculty may implement student engagement strategies to encourage teachers to implement innovative student engagement activities in online learning, such as interactive activities, multimedia resources, and collaborative projects to enhance the readiness, attitude, and perception of the medical students' satisfaction with online learning.

Medical students are also encouraged to use innovative strategies to actively appreciate online learning.

Future researchers may investigate similar topics, exploring other variables in different research setting with a broader scope and a bigger sample size.

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